

MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF
POLYMER COMPOSITES CONTAINING PLASMA-TREATED MICA

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A "Large Volume Microwave Plasma Generator" (LMP) has been used for surface treatment of phlogopite mica flakes in a variety of plasma environments. These have included polymerizable organic vapors such as styrene and ethylene, other active gases or gas mixtures, as well as inert gases. Plasma-treated surfaces have been examined by immersion calorimetry, and by other techniques.

Following plasma treatment, the mica flakes have been used as fillers in polystyrene (PS), polyethylene (PE), as well as in PE-PS mixtures.

The composites, usually containing 10% to 30% by weight of mica, (but in some instances up to 70 wt %) have been subjected to a variety of mechanical and electrical property evaluations. Among the former, tensile and impact strength have been measured. These tests show that ethylene and styrene-plasma treatments substantially enhance the mechanical properties of PE and PS based composites, respectively, whereas treatment in a "mismatched" plasma degrades these properties. This is consistent with the formation of a plasma polymer layer which can either act as a "bridge" between the polymer matrix and the mica filler, or else (in the case of mismatch due to "incompatible" polymers) prevents effective bonding.

Regarding electrical properties of the composites, the complex permittivity $\kappa^*(f)$, conductivity, and breakdown properties have been measured. As expected for the case of strong interfacial polarization effects, $\kappa^*(f)$ ($10^{-2} < f < 10^7$ Hz) depends sensitively upon the type of surface treatment and sample conditioning. The dispersion characteristics have been interpreted in terms of Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars theory.

Introduction

In recent years the use of polymer-based composites has become widespread in diverse applications. Among mineral fillers used in such composite materials, mica has been occupying an increasingly important place: for applications in electrical insulation systems, for example, mica has for many years been a well-known and well-proven insulating material. Furthermore, mica is relatively cheap, abundant, and does not present health hazards. In the present work we have used high aspect ratio phlogopite (Suzorite*) mica flakes from a Quebec deposit.

Whatever the eventual use of a particular polymer/mica composite, adhesion at the interface between the two media is crucial to overall performance characteristics; a variety of coupling agents and encapsulation technologies are being used to promote interfacial adhesion. We have developed a new surface treatment technique which consists of exposing the filler (mica) particles to a "cold" ($T_e/T_g \gg 1$) microwave plasma in a "Large Volume Microwave Plasma Generator"^g (LMP) apparatus (1), before incorporating them in the polymer matrix. This technique of surface modification is brief, simple, nonpolluting, and it involves only low-cost materials. It is based upon plasma chemistry which, as is now well-known, is useful in a variety of chemical reactions, depending upon the type of gas introduced into the plasma discharge (2). For instance, "cold" plasmas in organic vapors can yield a wide variety of plasma-polymerized, thin solid films (2-4) which generally adhere very well to solid substrates, are highly cross-linked, and can be made free from imperfections such as pinholes. Since, however, plasma polymers are sufficiently distinct from their conventional counterparts, it has been accepted (4) to identify them, for example, as "plasma-polymerized ethylene" (PPE), "plasma-polymerized styrene" (PPS), etc., when ethylene (E) or styrene (S) vapor, respectively, are used as the "monomer" in the plasma reaction.

In this paper we describe some aspects of the LMP treatment and its effect on interfacial properties of mica flakes. Following this, mechanical and electrical properties of polymer-mica composites are discussed as a function of various LMP treatments of the mica filler.

Plasma Treatment and Surface Properties

Screened fractions of mica flakes (-40 + 70 mesh) were placed in the LMP reactor tube and exposed to plasma treatments in various gases for durations ranging from 30 seconds up to 600 seconds. By rotating the reactor, the flakes were tumbled continuously, permitting uniform exposure of the surfaces to the plasma.

The ability of LMP treatment to modify the surface properties of various particulate materials, including mica flakes, has been documented earlier (5). Plasma-treated mica is quite distinct from untreated controls in terms of its wettability, as shown by calorimetric heat of immersion data reproduced in Table I from reference (5).

* Suzorite is a registered trademark of Marietta Resources International, Ltd.

Table I. Heats of Immersion of Mica in Water :
Effect of LMP Treatments (a).

Treatment	ΔH_{imm} (cal/g) @ 25°C
Control	0.092
Vacuum only	0.090
N ₂ plasma (b)	0.090
Ar " (b)	0.086
SO ₂ " (b)	0.078
C ₂ H ₄ " (b)	0.139
NH ₃ " (b)	0.107
SO ₂ " (c)	0.081
C ₂ H ₄ " (c)	0.134

(a) All data reproduced from ref. (5).
 (b) LMP at 2 torr and 90 sec.
 (c) LMP at 2 torr and 60 sec.

Clearly, plasma treatments may be used to favor either hydrophilic (Ar, SO₂ plasmas) or hydrophobic (C₂H₄ plasmas, viz Table I) effects, and this suggests that interfacial wetting by polymeric fluids may also be controlled through suitable plasma treatment of the solid (mica) surface. An exploratory study of this concept was reported earlier (6,7); it showed, as anticipated, that melt flow, tensile (6) and electrical (7) properties of mica-filled composites varied with the chemical nature of a plasma treatment and its intensity. In particular, it was demonstrated that E and S plasma treatments substantially enhance the mechanical properties of polyethylene (PE) and polystyrene (PS)-based composites, respectively, whereas treatment in a "mismatched" plasma degrades these properties. This is consistent with the formation of a plasma polymer layer which can either act as a "bridge" between the matrix and the filler, or else (in the case of mismatch due to the presumably incompatible polymers PPS/PE or PPE/PS) prevents effective bonding. We now elaborate on this earlier work by examining the elastic modulus and tensile impact behaviour of PS, PE and 1/1 mixtures of these polymers filled with variously treated micas.

Mechanical Properties

As in the earlier study (6,7) mica samples were subjected to plasmas of S and E monomers; dynamic pressures were maintained between 1 and 2 torr, and treatment times were restricted to 90 seconds. In a number of cases sequential treatments were administered, consisting of a 90-second exposure to E plasma followed by a 90-second S plasma treatment (E/S), or vice-versa (S/E). Following treatments, samples were "quenched" in the reactor for about one day in a dry nitrogen atmosphere, were then added to the molten polymer matrix, and dispersed in a Brabender Plasticorder at 190°C to give filled stocks of 10, 20 and 30 weight % filler content. These stocks were subsequently compression molded, and samples were cut from them for tensile impact and Instron testing. The elastic modulus was calculated from the latter experimental curve.

The elastic modulus versus mica loading behaviour is shown in Figures 1(a), (b) and (c) for PE, PS and 1/1 blend matrices, respectively. In the present low density PE matrix (Fig. 1 a) the untreated mica does not produce reinforcing effects, as was also reported by Woodhams et al. (8), though the decrease in modulus up to 20% loading is slight. The very obvious difference between the S and E-treated composites underscores the apparent importance of compatibility at the filler/matrix interface in the fabrication of reinforced composite structures : As mentioned above, it is reasonable to explain the substantial (more than 2-fold) rise in modulus for E-treatment

Fig. 1 - Elastic modulus of composites plotted against weight % of mica for (a) polyethylene (PE), (b) polystyrene (PS), and (c) a (1:1)PE-PS mixture. Symbols in brackets designate plasma treatments, as described in the text. Treatment duration was 90 sec throughout, except for sequential treatments (180 sec).

at 20% load in terms of a PPE coating on the mica surface, and resultant enhanced wetting by the molten PE matrix. Even more arresting is the behaviour of sequential S/E treatment : the characteristics of sequentially-treated fillers are further elaborated in connection with Figs. 1(b) and (c).

PS composites (Fig. 1 b) illustrate more dramatically the effect of plasma treatment, since the rather negative effects of adding untreated mica to this polymer are completely offset by suitable surface modification. As in the case of PE, "compatibilization" of the mica surface by S treatment has a beneficial effect on the elastic properties of the composite, but the major benefits of plasma treatment reside in the sequential procedure, particularly in the E/S sequence. We speculate that the longer plasma exposure in the

sequential procedures more effectively encapsulates the mica flakes, and thus reduces the occurrence of uncoated mica-polymer contacts. This hypothesis is strengthened by the data of Fig. 1(c). PE and PS are known to be incompatible (9), and neither untreated, nor E-treated mica enhances the modulus of the pair. Clearly an S-based surface coating is generally more favorable, but once again major improvement is noted when sequentially-treated mica is used as filler. We may speculate in this case that the presence of both PPE and PPS sites on the mica surface permit the filler to act rather effectively as a bridging agent, with significant modification of the incompatibility problem.

The tensile impact data of Table II provide additional support for these views.

Table II. Effect of Plasma Treatment on Tensile Impact Performance of Mica-Filled Composites.

Filler		(Data normalized to value of pertinent control)		
		Tensile Impact (ft-lb/in)		
wt %	Treatment	PE	PS	PE/PS(1/1)
-	-	18.6	0.20	0.96
Normalized value		1.00	1.00	1.00
10	-	0.097	1.18	0.65
20	-	0.055	1.13	0.47
10	S	0.044	2.90	0.73
10	E	0.206	0.65	0.56
10	S/E	0.180	2.55	1.86
10	E/S	0.172	2.88	2.22

The initial high impact resistance of PE is severely reduced by mica addition; E, S/E and E/S-treated micas show some improvement while a S-treatment of the solid further worsens this performance parameter. S, and sequential treatments strongly enhance the inherently brittle characteristics of PS, but the most interesting data again are those for E/S and S/E treated mica composites of the 1/1 PS/PE mixture. The coupling effect of the "bifunctional" mica surfaces is here clearly shown, since only these micas are capable of actually toughening the incompatible and weak polymer mixture.

Electrical Properties

Since early in this work it was felt that studies of the dielectric properties of polymer/mica composites would be of interest from several points of view :

- (i) Firstly, dielectric permittivity measurements, in particular the interfacial polarization or "Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars" (MWS) effect, should sensitively reflect attempts to control the properties of the polymer-filler interface by plasma treatment.
- (ii) Secondly, it was felt that mica flakes might act as barriers to the propagation of "electrical trees" in the polymer matrix, thus conceivably imparting superior high voltage endurance characteristics to the composite dielectrics.

Results pertaining to (i) and (ii) have already been reported in references (7) and (10), respectively.

From this earlier work it was found that the dielectric behaviour is quite complex despite the fact that the composites in question are, a priori, rather ideal "MWS" dielectrics (see below). Furthermore, among all the testing methods we have used to date to evaluate sample quality, high voltage endurance and corona-initiation tests have proven to be by far the most sensitive: defects in the samples such as residual gas bubbles, or even microvoids due to incomplete wetting at the polymer/mica interface lead to very substantial performance degradation. The reason for this is, of course, that these high voltage tests specifically "seek out" the "weak points" in a sample, whereas other test methods tend to "average" the parameter being measured.

Since the earlier-reported (7) measurements of the relative complex permittivity, $\kappa^*(\omega) [= \kappa'(\omega) - j\kappa''(\omega)]$, much additional work has been done. In particular, more detailed investigations have been made of dielectric loss mechanisms, such as those resulting from moisture absorption by the composite, the effect upon $\kappa^*(\omega)$ of plasma surface treatment and of sample conditioning in general. Some of the results are reported here.

Fig. 2 - Photomicrographs of a PE + 10 weight % mica sample. (a) Transverse sectional view of a compression-molded plaque. The dark, oblong shapes are mica flakes. (b) Same sample, viewed in the plane of the plaque.

In view of the very important role of PE in electrical insulation technology, recent work has been restricted to PE/mica composites. 2 mm thick sample plaques are produced by compression molding mixtures of PE powder (U.S.I. "Microthene") and mica flakes at 190°C and 10,000 psi. As can be seen in the photomicrographs, figures 2(a) and (b), the flakes become oriented during the molding process in such a way that their long axis is parallel to the plane of the plaque. Recalling that the flakes were selected from a (-40 + 70 mesh) screened fraction, their sizes and shapes are quite uniform: Based on a large number of measurements, they can be assimilated (with reasonable accuracy) to oblate spheroids having an average axial ratio $a/b = 0.074$. The composite, consequently, resembles a bicomponent, heterogeneous dielectric composed of the PE matrix (medium 1) and dispersed mica "spheroids" (medium 2), precisely the case treated by Sillars' generalized theory of the "Maxwell-Wagner" effect (11).

The literature on heterogeneous dielectrics up to the late 1960's, including Sillars' theory, is covered in an excellent review article by van Beek (12). Sillars' formulæ pertaining to the present case have already been reported (7) and will not be repeated here, but for one exception:

The high-frequency value of the permittivity is given by

$$\kappa_{\infty}' = \kappa_1' \left\{ \frac{\kappa_1' + [A_a(1 - V_2) + V_2](\kappa_2' - \kappa_1')}{\kappa_1' + A_a(1 - V_2)(\kappa_2' - \kappa_1')} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts 2 and 1 refer to the filler and the matrix, respectively. ($A_a = 0.89$ in the present case).

It is interesting to point out (as has been done in a very clear manner by van Beek (12)) that a separate body of theoretical work, completely divorced from MWS theory, has been concerned with calculating the permittivities of dielectric mixtures. The most general theory, that of Polder and van Santen (13), yields for flat oblate spheroids [$A_i = (1 - 2\delta, \delta, \delta), \delta < < 1$]

$$\kappa_{\infty}' = \kappa_1' + \frac{1}{3} V_2 (\kappa_2' - \kappa_1') \bar{\kappa}_1' \left[\frac{2}{\bar{\kappa}_1' + \delta(\kappa_2' - \bar{\kappa}_1')} + \frac{1}{\kappa_2' - 2\delta(\kappa_2' - \bar{\kappa}_1')} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\kappa}_1' \approx \kappa_1'$.

As will be shown below, permittivity measurements for the PE/mica system provide a good opportunity to test the relative merits of the theoretical expressions (1) and (2).

In figures 3(a) and (b), $\log(\kappa' - \kappa_{\infty}')$ and $\log \kappa''$ are plotted against $\log f$. The measurement techniques used have already been described elsewhere (7). In addition, ultra-low frequency measurements have been carried out (to 10^{-5} Hz; since they have little bearing on the present discussion, they are not shown in figure 3). In figures 4(a) and (b), values of κ' and κ'' at selected frequencies have, respectively, been plotted as a function of mica concentration (% mica by volume = $100 V_2$). The mica used for fabricating these samples had been dried in a vacuum oven, but not plasma treated. The effect of this latter treatment upon $\kappa^*(\omega)$ will be discussed below.

For the sake of brevity, only the salient features of figures 3 and 4 can be discussed here :

a) Measurements of $\kappa'(f)$ and $\kappa''(f)$ on pure mica samples show the same monotonic behaviour as the curves in figure 3(a) and (b), a fact which suggests that the dominant features of this figure are due to the intrinsic dielectric properties of mica. This is indeed verified by figure 4 : κ' and κ'' vary linearly with mica concentration (within experimental accuracy) over the entire frequency range studied. The dielectric properties of mica, far too complex a subject to discuss here, are being studied as a separate topic in our laboratory (14).

b) In figure 4(a) the theoretical curves corresponding to equations (1) and (2) may be compared with experimental values of " κ_{∞}' " (data at 10^5 Hz - as seen from figure 3(a) these exceed values corresponding to our highest frequency measurements by less than 3%). Whereas (2) predicts a linear relationship between κ_{∞}' and V_2 , as indeed observed experimentally, (1) yields significantly better numerical agreement with experimental data, even though it deviates from linearity, particularly at high V_2 values.

c) Since the earlier work (7) it has become clear that sample "conditioning" can have a greater effect up on $\kappa^*(\omega)$ than was initially expected. By this we mean primarily conditions of relative humidity to which samples are exposed preceding and during dielectric measurements, for these govern the

Fig. 3- Plots of (a) $\log(\kappa' - \kappa_{\infty}')$ and (b) $\log \kappa''$ versus \log frequency for a series of PE-mica composites containing 0 to 70% by weight of mica. The samples were conditioned at 50% relative humidity, except for the dotted curves in (b) corresponding to samples which had been immersed in distilled water.

Fig. 4- Plots of (a) κ' and (b) κ'' versus volume percentage of mica, for a series of different measurement frequencies. The broken curves in (a) represent the theoretical equations (1) and (2) in the text.

sorption of moisture by the sample itself : As a rather extreme example, figure 5 shows gravimetrically determined moisture contents for samples of various mica concentrations, after these had been immersed in distilled water for time intervals ranging from 1 hr to 168 hrs (1 week). Clearly, heavily filled samples are more susceptible to water uptake, since it readily diffuses along interfacial boundaries, where much of it also accumulates.

It is now recognized that the broad loss-peak centred near 1 kHz (7) (see figure 3 b) is essentially a MWS loss due to sample humidity, in agreement with the literature (12). This sample series had been conditioned by storage for 196 hrs at 25°C and 50% relative humidity. The loss peak could not be eliminated by any of the drying procedures attempted; on the other hand, its amplitude could be very substantially increased by immersion in distilled water, as illustrated for two samples in figure 3 b (dashed curves).

d) Unlike the presence of water, which can cause κ'' to vary by an order of magnitude or even much more, plasma treatment of the mica flakes has only a relatively minor effect. This is illustrated in figure 6, where $\tan \delta$ ($\equiv \kappa''/\kappa'$) at two frequencies (0.1 and 100 Hz) is plotted as a function of exposure time to an E plasma. Although the curves are qualitatively similar, the effect is much more evident at 0.1 Hz : $\tan \delta$ is decreased by a factor of roughly 2 by a 180 sec. plasma treatment, then increases again towards a constant value. These observations can only be explained in rather speculative terms at the present time.

Fig. 5 - Plot of weight % water versus % mica by volume for a series of PE-mica composite samples, after these had been immersed in distilled water for time intervals ranging from 1 to 168 hours.

Fig. 6 - $\tan \delta (\equiv \kappa''/\kappa')$ of PE-20 wt % mica composites, in which the mica had been subjected to ethylene plasma treatments of differing durations. Curves for two measuring frequencies (0.1 and 100 Hz) are shown.

Conclusion

High aspect ratio phlogopite mica flakes have been treated in microwave plasmas of ethylene (E) or styrene (S), or they were given sequential (E/S) or (S/E) treatments. This results in the formation of a thin, strongly adhering plasma-polymer film on the mica surface. Following treatment, the flakes have been incorporated as filler in PE, PS or a PE-PS mixture; filler contents up to 30% (in some instances as high as 70%) by weight of mica have been used for most experiments.

Mechanical (Elastic modulus, tensile impact) and electrical (complex permittivity) measurements on plasma-treated and untreated (control) samples of these composite materials are reported. Plasma treatment may either "compatibilize" the mica/polymer pair, leading to enhanced mechanical properties, or may have no beneficial effect on these when the plasma-polymer and the matrix are "mismatched".

Electrical measurements can also serve as a useful index of sample quality, and have the additional benefit of being non-destructive (with the exception of dielectric breakdown tests). Permittivity measurements of PE/mica composites have been found to agree well with dielectric theory; although these materials may have potential uses in electrical insulation technology, their tendency to absorb moisture and thus raise the dielectric losses (particularly at 60 Hz), would be a drawback.

Finally, the possibility of producing complex surface modification of fillers by LMP treatment warrants further detailed study, both for its applied potential as well as to provide answers to numerous interesting scientific questions.

Nomenclature

T_e	electron temperature
T_g	gas temperature
κ^*	complex relative permittivity
κ'	relative permittivity
κ_{∞}'	high frequency value of κ'
κ''	relative loss factor
f	frequency
ω	angular frequency (= $2\pi f$)
a, b, c	ellipsoid major axes
A_i, δ	depolarizing factors
V_2	volume fraction of filler

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